

A Study on the Impact of Cross-Culture Contrasts in Universal Promoting

Student Name: Afia Tazaine H

Course: III B.com Accounting & Finance

Institution: Women's Christian College (Affiliated with the University of Madras)

Abstract:- This period of globalization has driven the integration and extension of different economies and this integration of economies has uncovered the businesses within the economy within the economy to all universal cultural marketing mix. Competition between the businesses at the universal market level has caused an increase in the market that keeps up and improves the significance of commerce in their target advertise. The centrality of social differences is on a high level and the credit goes to unused and advanced technologies which make the marketers able to induce the largest clients and widest customers past the geographical area. This research paper concentrates on the impacts of contrasts in culture in B2B integrating market communication channels. This paper also characterizes the B2B markets in detail and additionally coordinates marketing communication channels and the hypothetical system of this paper will be based on SET.

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization nowadays has led to growth and a fusion of different economics. The intersection of economics demonstrates that the field's business is a synthesis of universal cultures (Shankar et al., 2021). The competition among firms in the global market, which upholds and enhances the importance of business in the target market, has helped to increase market research. The importance of diversity in business culture is steadily growing, and the development of new and cutting-edge technologies is to thank for this. These technologies enable marketers to connect with a variety of diverse audiences beyond the confines of physical locations (Cortez et al., 2020).

The marketing communication channels and new technologies have elevated the importance of research on social differences in commerce. According to the differences between nations, there are also differences in communicating culture. This may lead businesses to break individuals from different cultures at the time they advertise their brands within the worldwide markets. Businesses ought to know the truth that different cultural patterns of different economics influence the promotion and marketing of their products. The consumer choices moreover in several economies depend on the traditions, cultural values, and customs of that particular region.

➤ Objectives

- To know the cultural differences through the conceptual resource.
- To assess the cultural differences in international marketing.
- To explore the way how cultural differences can affect the application of marketing techniques and consumer behaviors.
- To comprehend the different characteristics of business-to-business integrated marketing communication channels and also the importance of their culture.
- To analyze the business-to-business marketplaces with the utilization of SET or Social Exchange Theory.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

➤ Article 1

Impact of COVID-19 on consumer behavior: Will the ancient propensities return or pass on?

The purpose of this research report is to study changing consumer behavior. As discussed by the author Sheth, (2020), the consumer habits of buying and shopping are disturbed by the social distancing, lockdown, and trade barriers in the COVID-19 pandemic that has affected humanity worldwide. Consumers are adopting and learning new habits and improvising their purchasing behavior. For example, before the COVID-19 pandemic, people used to visit stores to purchase goods and services and now they have improvised their behavior by purchasing goods and services online through various e-commerce websites where stores come to the home (Sheth, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic gave a boost to online shopping. If consumers return to the old traditional habits of visiting the shop to purchase products, then they have to follow new and modified rules and regulations and new procedures in the traditional way customers used to shop before the COVID-19 pandemic. New technologies will also boost new habits of purchasing products and services online. It will also change demographics.

➤ Article 2

Cross-cultural varieties in buyer behavior: A writing audit of universal studies.

The authors of Timokhina et al., (2018) of this article have discussed the effects on consumer behavior of cross-cultural variations. The cross-cultural variations are related to the differences between the values and norms of different countries. Cross-cultural variations refer to the norms, values, superstitions, lifestyles, traditions, and many more. It also

refers to the demographic differences that include income, age, and gender. This difference is because consumers from different countries have different aspirations and different values. The major objective of this article is to study the analysis of cross-cultural consumers and to identify the similarities and dissimilarities between the consumers of two or more communities (Timokhina et al., 2018). The aim of understanding similarities and dissimilarities that dwell between different states and countries is important to Multinational Corporations (MNCs), which must develop various strategies to fulfill the needs and wants of the consumers in a particular foreign market.

➤ **Article 3**

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and its effect on customer conduct.

There is extremely fierce competition in the current economic context that is aimed at retaining and winning different consumer segments. It is also directed by an exceptional boost in technological advancements. The efforts of marketers in executing new ways of communicating (Duralia, 2018). Demand is the only path to success in the business. Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) is considered the clearest and most visible part of the activities related to marketing. Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) contributes to grabbing the attention of both buyers and sellers, especially those buyers and sellers who require information from different sources to make their purchase decisions. Hence, the article aims to focus on the major tools which are used by the specialists in Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) in their efforts to build an efficient and permanent relationship with the customers and actual consumers as discussed by the author Duralia, (2018). The article has also evaluated the secondary data sources regarding the effects of the false news that was made through different media channels on consumer perceptions.

➤ **Article 4**

A Brief Examination on Culture and Behaviour in Cutting edge Trade Relations-Basics, Significance and Comparison.

The author of this article Apstsiauri, (2020) has discussed the importance of knowledge of the cultural aspects in the relations of modern international business by considering broad and limited approaches that are practical to this topic. The openness of the new growth markets in the developing countries of Asia, development of free trade, free movement of capital, investments, labor force, and development of new technologies have created exceptional opportunities for global economic Eastern countries and western countries' partnerships in equal (Apstsiauri, 2020). In the opinion of the author, some features of cultural components of business relations are underestimated, mostly when the geography of regions and countries, number of actors, and scope of cultural experiences of businesses are

gradually developing. Further, the study covers the improvement of modern business culture and minimizes the risk of unsuccessful business activities at both the corporate level and government level.

➤ **Article 5**

The modern period of working environment connections: Is the social trade hypothesis still important?

In this article, the authors Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, (2018) have argued about the changes in the workplace since the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the world and humanity. It has also affected the relationships at the workplace and has necessitated adjustments in the traditional working conditions. It has given rise to work-from-home jobs. It has also changed labor relationships to political, technological, globalization, and economical changes. The study also investigates the changes in the psychological theories in place of labor approaches or industrial approaches (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2018). The study has reviewed 4 major areas where the SET (Social Exchange Theory) model has been executed that address recent trends that question the traditional SET (Social Exchange Theory) theory and has proposed different theories or models. There are many changes in workplace features. The author has referred to these theories as a combination as they merge traditional SET (Social Exchange Theory) premises with new workplace features.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Population*

The population of this study is individuals who work in different companies with various job roles in several cities or counties.

➤ *Sample*

The sample size of this study is 40.

➤ *Sampling Technique*

The sampling technique used in this study is Cluster sampling under non-probability sampling.

➤ *Data Collection Method*

The data of this study has been collected from both primary and secondary data sources.

• *Primary Data*

Primary data has been collected via structured questionnaires in the form of google forms from respondents from various cities or countries.

• *Secondary Data*

Secondary data is collected from research articles, journals, websites, blogs, etc.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: SOCIOECONOMICS

PARTICULARS	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Gender	Male	26	10.4%
	Female	18	7.2%
	Transgender	Nil	Nil
Age	18-20	4	1.6%
	20-25	23	9.2%
	25-30 & Above 30	15	6%

Table 1: Shows the generic information about the respondents which is gender and age.

Table 2: Socioeconomics of individuals (Company, Job role, cities/countries)

COMPANIES			
Active Communications International	Cognizant	Indigo	KK Wind Solutions
Maruti Suzuki	NatWest	Ovantica	Reitmans
Tata Starbucks	Unilever	Walmart	Tata Consultancy Services
JOB ROLES			
AVP	Associate	Customer Service	Financial Analyst
Information Technology	Operational Analyst	Restaurant manager	Senior Analyst
Senior Sponsorship Executive	Shift Supervisor	Team leader	Trainee engineer

Table 2: Represents the types of companies and job roles that individuals work.

Table 3: Respondents' views on cross-culture differences affecting international marketing and SET (Social Exchange Theory)

PARTICULARS	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY
Awareness of the term cross-culture or cultural differences	Yes	68.2%
	No	11.4%
	Maybe	20.5%
Cultural differences affecting international marketing strategies or techniques	Yes	72.7%
	No	15.9%
	Maybe	11.4%
Cultural differences affecting business to business.	Yes	88.4%
	No	9.3%
	Maybe	2.3%
Awareness of the term SET or Social Exchange Theory	Yes	40.9%
	No	43.2%
	Maybe	15.9%
Acceptance that the SET can integrate a strong connection with the organizational practices and provide proper consumer satisfaction	Yes	58.6%
	No	9.1%
	Maybe	34.1%

Table 3: Indicates that a maximum number of people are aware of cross-culture or cultural differences and SET or Social Exchange Theory answered different questions regarding the study and The cultural differences affecting international marketing in various factors.

V. CONCLUSION

B2B refers to the business transaction between businesses like between a retailer and a distributor or between a distributor and a manufacturer. The complete volume of b2b transactions is higher compared to the exchange of b2c

transactions. After analyzing the diverse viewpoints of culture which leave an impact on the promoting techniques adopted by the company, the marketing teams of the company should consider and survey the culture (Kingshott et al.,2020). The marketing team of the company should inspect the various groups of people which make up their target market. Moreover, promoters utilizing the communication channels should be considered as the cultural elements of the target gather. Any future studies on the topic should consider the effect of the socio-economic aspects of a group and its impact on the promoting channels that are being utilized. The challenges that have been confronted in cultural research are

the availability of the data and information for the expansion of culture. For example, people who live in the same areas or locations can also have diverse cultures. And people who live in the same geographical area can also have different religious views, and customs among other cultural aspects. A group should not be judged by marketers just because it is from a particular geological zone.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Develop a social/cultural environment

This research paper is just scratching the surface of introducing the main feature of business to business and the cultural elements of the communication channel of integrated marketing (Cartwright et al.,2021). The social environment consists of the influence of religious, family, educational, and social systems in the marketing frameworks. Marketers who intend to showcase their products abroad may be very sensitive to foreign cultures.

While the contrasts between our cultural background in the United States and those of foreign nations may seem small, marketers who ignore these contrasts risk failure in implementing promoting programs.

Failure to consider social contrasts is one of the essential reasons for promoting disappointments overseas.

B. Language

It is one of the major cultural differences in marketing that companies need to understand before promoting their products and services in different foreign countries (Cooley,2018). It can be seen that in the past times that numerous major mistakes have happened because of translation issues which have caused many numerous destructive impacts.

Example: Chevrolet made a car called the Chevy Nova. This car was exceptionally well known in the United States, but when they attempted to sell them in Spanish-speaking countries, they appeared to have problems because NO VA implies 'no go' so they thought the car would not move. If companies are going to sell their items globally, they need to think about what their title implies in the countries where they want to sell them. (Lucy Fasano, 2020)

C. and Taboos

All cultures have their own special set of traditions and taboos. Marketers need to memorize these traditions and taboos so that they will know what is acceptable and what is not for their promoting programs.

Example: In certain nations, an endless majority of Muslims discover drinking alcohol as sinful. Hence, marketing liquor would not only result in lower sales but also may get the company in trouble with the individuals in the country who may be extremely outraged that alcohol is being marketed in a positive light. However, in America, beer commercials appear to be the norm and can be seen whenever you turn on the television or on advertisements online. (Charles DeWilde, 2020)

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